

Deliverable D6.1 (D26)

RNAct website and social media networks online

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RNAct MSCA-ITN project 813239

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The RNAct project

RNAct is a EU-MSCA ITN project with as research aim the design of novel **RNA recognition motif (RRM)** proteins for exploitation in synthetic biology and bio-analytics. We use **computational approaches** to analyse proteins and RNA, and test newly designed RRM in large-scale experiments. Viable RRM are studied with integrative **structural biology**, and will be applied in **synthetic biology** and in **bio-analytics**.

See <http://rnact.eu/> for more information.

Project partners

(Coordinator)

(Academic)

(Commercial)

About this document

This reports deliverable D6.1 (D26) of the RNAct MSCA-ITN project. It was prepared by:

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Social media channels

In terms of social media, the Twitter channel **@eu_rnact** was initiated for use by the project. A Facebook page about the project will be initiated by the ESRs, and we will add material to YouTube (webinars) as it becomes available. It is important that these are initiated by the ESRs, and we will organize a session during the first workshop to enable them to do so. We will also continue to discuss other options for advertising the project as it starts up.